

ISic0919

I.Sicily inscription 0919

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble ('bardiglio')

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,system

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140400

1. □ τόπος □
2. Εἰρήνης
3. καὶ Θεοδού-
4. λου. □ □ □
5. □ □
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492549

EDCS 39102076

PHI 140400

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0919>
DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4340068](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340068)

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0919. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385333>